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THE ISSUE OF ADMINISTRATIVE LIABILITY FOR ILLEGAL CUTTING, DAMAGE AND DESTRUCTION OF FOREST PLANTATIONS IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

This article reflects some of the gaps in the current legislation of Ukraine on forest protection. The problem of deforestation in the world is extremely acute, as it leads to dangerous climate change. World politics is focused on measures to combat and prevent deforestation. The forest industry of domestic legislation also requires close attention. The development of this industry and taking into account global trends will contribute to the satisfaction of one of the key rights of citizens to a safe environment for life and health and to compensation for harm caused by the violation of this right. The composition of the administrative offense associated with illegal logging, damage and destruction of forest crops and young growth is analyzed and proposals are made to improve the Ukrainian administrative legislation in the field of forest protection. It is proposed to make appropriate changes to the current administrative legislation and to introduce the sale of illegally cut trees or shrubs into alternative actions of the objective side.

Keywords: forest plantations, illegal logging, administrative responsibility, forest fund

Introduction. Ukraine, as an independent state governed by the rule of law, is actively pursuing efforts to Europeanize national legislation and make European Union standards a priority. One of the areas of law that is a priority today is the forest sector. However, the rules establishing liability for offenses in the field of forest protection in Ukraine are outdated and unacceptable in modern realities, which may be the cause of environmental and legal nihilism. The problem of deforestation in the world is extremely acute, as it leads to climate change, so at the COP26 climate summit, world leaders decided to stop deforestation by 2030 [1].

In addition, floods and droughts are becoming more frequent. One of the reasons for this state of affairs is global climate change, according to scientists from the Ukrainian Hydrometeorological Institute [2], there is now a clear trend to increase the annual surface water runoff, but decrease this figure in the spring. Due to warming in winter, the duration decreases and in spring, due to the fact that less snow melts and less rain falls, there is a decrease in runoff. This leads to a decrease in the level of soil moisture and, as a consequence, to a shortage of drinking and industrial water, even in the mountainous settlements of the Carpathians,

where the highest amount of precipitation falls in Ukraine. According to forecasts made by 2050, this trend will only intensify [3].

Methodology. The purpose of the article is to analyze the composition of the administrative offense related to illegal logging, damage and destruction of forest crops and young animals and to formulate proposals for improving administrative legislation in the field of forest protection.

Main part. According to estimates by the World Wildlife Fund (WWF), in 40 years the bio resources of the planet Earth will be completely depleted. With forests in the world, the situation is the worst. Forests are destroyed in a matter of days and grow for decades. Therefore, we need to think about how we should replenish natural resources in order to restore the ecological balance. [4] During 2014-2018, state forest protection units identified 31.7 thousand cases of illegal deforestation, as a result of which 106.9 thousand m³ of forest were cut down [5]. The figure shows the number and volume of illegal logging for 2010-2018 (blue - the number of cases in thousands of pieces, orange - the volume of illegal logging in thousands of cubic meters).

Illegal deforestation has become the most common crime against the environment, according to statistics from the Prosecutor General's Office of Ukraine, the dynamics of crime in this area is increasing: in 2019 - 1961 criminal offenses were registered, 227 of which were criminal offenses; in 2020 - 2553/519 criminal offenses; in 2021 - 1961/227 criminal offenses [6].

According to the Forest Code of Ukraine, the Forest Fund of Ukraine includes land plots of the forest fund, namely:

- forest (both covered and not covered with forest vegetation, but subject to afforestation, as well as occupied by forest paths, clearings, firebreaks);
- non-forest (occupied by structures related to forestry, power lines, product pipelines; underground communications; agricultural land provided for forestry needs; swamps, reservoirs within the forest land plots provided for forestry needs).

The forest fund of Ukraine includes forest plots, including protective plantations of the linear type, with an area of at least 0.1 hectares.

The forest fund of Ukraine does not include:

- green plantations within settlements (parks, gardens, squares, boulevards, etc.), which are not assigned to forests in the prescribed manner;
- individual trees and groups of trees, shrubs on agricultural lands, homesteads, cottages and gardens [7].

If it is necessary to cut down trees near municipal property, it is necessary to obtain a permit from the relevant municipal authorities. Administrative liability for illegal felling and damage to trees or shrubs; transportation, storage of illegally felled trees or shrubs; destruction or damage of forest crops, seedlings or saplings in forest nurseries and plantations, as well as young animals of natural origin and self-seeding in areas designated for reforestation, provided by Article 65 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of Ukraine "Illegal felling, damage and destruction of forest crops

and young [8]. The fines for these illegal actions were revised by the legislator in 2019 and today amount to thirty to sixty non-taxable minimum incomes of citizens and officials - from one hundred and fifty to three hundred non-taxable minimum incomes. When re-offending, a fine is imposed on citizens from sixty to ninety non-taxable minimum incomes and on officials - from six hundred to nine hundred non-taxable minimum incomes [9].

For a comprehensive analysis it is necessary to carry out a legal analysis of an administrative offense. The object of this administrative offense are public relations, ensuring the protection, rational use and reproduction of the forest fund. The subject should be considered forest diversity, trees, shrubs, plants of artificial and natural origin, growing in areas belonging to the forest fund. It is important that the subject is both the vegetation that is at the root, and felled trees and shrubs. The objective side of the specified offense is representation in the form of illegal actions, such as:

- felling
- damage
- destruction
- transportation
- storage

It is necessary to reveal the essence of illegal actions, Yes, illegal logging, in our opinion, is logging without proper permission. According to the current legislation, the appropriate permit is a logging ticket or a forest ticket. According to Article 69 of the Forest Code of Ukraine, this is a special permit for the use of forest resources (including logging) on a designated forest area. The logging ticket for logging is issued by the forestry, and for felling of the main use - by the Office. The procedure for registration, storage, filling of logging tickets (warrants) and forest tickets is established by the Ministry of Forestry of Ukraine in coordination with the Ministry of Nature of Ukraine and the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. Permits for special use

of forest resources are issued by the bodies of the Ministry of Forestry of Ukraine. The procedure for felling is regulated by the Rules of felling for the main use in the forests of Ukraine, the Rules of felling related to forestry, and other felling, approved by resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers. Damage - the task of a certain damage to a tree or shrub, which stops the growth or worsens the condition of plants. Destruction - complete elimination, cessation of forest resources. Transportation and storage of illegally felled trees or shrubs - movement of felled trees and shrubs without proper permission and storage in a certain place.

The subjects of the analyzed administrative offense are natural sane persons who have reached 16 years of age, and who according to Art. 14 of the Code of Administrative Offenses are subject to administrative liability for offenses and related to non-compliance with the rules and regulations, the implementation of which is part of their official duties. Those who have a certain official position perform official duties, ie special subjects have a stricter responsibility. In addition, not only administrative but also disciplinary liability is applied to such offenders. This may be primarily the case for forest officials. We are talking about certain positions mentioned directly in the articles of the Administrative Code, and about officials of enterprises, institutions and organizations, regardless of ownership. In most cases, the relevant authorities must proceed from their duties to comply with certain rules. Thus, we can talk not only about official crimes (official criminal offenses), but also official administrative offenses.

Special attention should be paid to administrative offenses from the point of view that there are conflicts of personal and departmental interests. On the one hand, the profitability of the enterprise is important, on the other - non-compliance with various administrative rules - safety, fire, sanitary, environmental requirements, because it is expensive. Such rules are included in job descriptions, have internal and external nature, the state monitors compliance with mandatory administrative rules through special supervisory bodies and protects them in a number of areas of law. It is important to adopt international experience and introduce administrative liability of legal entities for violations in the field of nature protection.

The subjective side of illegal logging, damage and destruction of forest crops and young animals is presented in the form of guilt, namely intent or negligence, as well as the motives and purposes of the offense. According to Art. 10 of the Code of Administrative Offenses, an administrative offense is considered to have been committed intentionally when the person who committed it was aware of the illegal nature of his action or inaction, foresaw its harmful consequences and wanted them or knowingly allowed them to occur; Art. 11 of the Code of Administrative Offenses defines its commission through negligence, when the person who committed it foresaw the possibility of harmful consequences of his action, but recklessly relied on their prevention or did not foresee the possibility of such consequences, although he should and could have foreseen them [8]. Thus, the offender may act intentionally, ie aware of the illegality of actions, violation of certain

rules and procedures for nature protection, the environment; or carelessly - be aware of the risk of dangerous behavior and the consequences of such behavior for nature and the environment. The person will be responsible for the obligation to anticipate the negative consequences and prevent such consequences. There is also a careless form of guilt, when it can harm public interests, the subject is also aware of the purpose, nature, but in contrast to the intention does not provide any other result of their actions (inaction), in addition to which it expects and does not provide the possibility of socially dangerous consequences. In the case of a negligent form of guilt, a person anticipates the consequences of his behavior, but only neutral or useful, in his opinion, consequences may be, even socially harmful, but not socially dangerous (criminally punishable), which a person anticipates when intentionally acting (inaction) [11].

The distinction between administrative and criminal liability reveals some legislative gaps. Thus, for illegal felling of trees or shrubs in forests, protective and other forest plantations, transportation, storage, sale of illegally felled trees or shrubs that have caused significant damage, liability under Art. 246 of the Criminal code of Ukraine "Illegal felling or illegal transportation, storage, sale of wood" [12]. Stricter liability for acts committed repeatedly or by prior conspiracy by a group of persons; committed in reserves or in the territories or objects of the nature reserve fund, or in other specially protected forests; or if they have caused serious consequences. The note to the article provides a definition of significant harm and serious consequences. Significant damage is considered to be damage that is twenty times or more higher than the non-taxable minimum income of citizens, or other significant damage caused to the environment in terms of ensuring effective protection, proper protection, rational use and reproduction of forests. In 2022, the non-taxable minimum income of citizens for the qualification of criminal offenses is 1240.50 hryvnias [13]. Accordingly, the criminal penalty is damage from illegal logging or illegal transportation, storage, sale of forests in the amount of 24,810 hryvnias. Severe consequences are considered to be those consequences that are sixty or more times higher than the non-taxable minimum income of citizens, which is respectively 74,430 hryvnias.

Administrative liability is provided for the following violations of forest legislation: illegal use of lands of the state forest fund; violation of the established procedure for the use of the logging fund, harvesting and export of wood, harvesting of resin; illegal logging, damage and destruction of forest crops and young animals; destruction or damage of protective forest strips and protective forest plantations; destruction or damage of undergrowth in forests; implementation of forest uses not in accordance with the purpose or requirements provided for in the logging ticket (warrant) or forest ticket; violation of the rules of restoration and improvement of forests, use of mature wood resources; damage to hayfields and pastures on the lands of the state forest fund; unauthorized haymaking and cattle grazing, unauthorized harvesting of wild fruits, nuts,

mushrooms, berries; commissioning of production facilities without equipment that prevents harmful effects on forests; damage to forests by sewage, chemicals, oil and oil products, harmful emissions, waste and debris; littering of forests with waste; destruction or damage of forest drainage ditches, drainage systems and roads on the lands of the state forest fund; destruction or damage of demarcation signs in forests; destruction of forest fauna; violation of fire safety requirements in forests, unauthorized burning of vegetation or its remains. However, administrative legislation does not provide for liability for forest sales. That is, if illegal actions in the form of felling, damage, destruction, transportation, storage do not constitute significant damage, namely 24,810 hryvnias, administrative liability is provided for such actions. However, if the actions concern the sale of illegally felled forests, and do not constitute the above-mentioned significant damage, they do not entail either criminal or administrative liability.

Findings. The problem of deforestation in the world is extremely acute, as it leads to dangerous climate change. World policy is focused on measures to combat and prevent deforestation. The forest sector of domestic legislation also needs close attention. The development of this industry and taking into account global trends will contribute to the satisfaction of one of the key rights of citizens to a safe environment for life and health and to compensation for damage caused by the violation of this right.

The composition of the administrative offense related to illegal logging, damage and destruction of forest crops and young animals was analyzed and proposals were made to improve the administrative legislation in the field of forest protection. Thus, we propose to make appropriate changes to the current administrative legislation and present a new version of the article:

Article 65. Illegal felling, damage, destruction and sale of forest crops and young animals

Illegal felling and damage to trees or shrubs; transportation, storage of illegally felled trees or shrubs and their sale; destruction or damage of forest crops, seedlings or saplings in forest nurseries and plantations, as well as young animals of natural origin and self-seeding in areas designated for reforestation. This idea needs further development and scientific discussion.

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